

MARKETING OPPORTUNITIES IN BUILDING A SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS

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Abstract: Sustainable living is getting popular since, people are becoming more environmentally friendly. To begin, most of the market is saturated, thus paying attention to the issues which people are sensitive is vital for the organizations in order to keep their minimum market share. In other words, as much as people show their interest in sustainability, the organizations should more involve their program and marketing strategies in it. Moreover, since the new generation of communication tools, especially internet was introduced, interpersonal communication has been changed. For instance, social media give more opportunities to people for keeping in touch and exchange their point of view regarding the special issues. In addition, by increasing the popularity of the social media, people's awareness are increasing and consequently organizations inevitably should link their programs and businesses objectives to them; because they are able to drive organizational performance to the proper way.

Key words: Sustainability, Marketing, Social media, Marketing opportunities.

The concept of sustainability has been known since approximately 30 years ago due to increasing global awareness. While in the past few researchers maintain that sustainability is possible by decreasing production and consumption (Jones, Clarke-Hill, Comfort, & Hillier, 2008), marketing efforts are directed towards increasing them; the link between marketing and sustainability really close. In fact, Baldassarre & Campo (2016) notes that poor sustainability behavior directly reduced sales and profits. There are various concerns expressed in regard to marketing strategy as time progresses, and companies always strive to take on various strategies to gain competitive advantages in the market. Sustainability has become an area of concern for companies as they pursue growth and development (Kumar, Rahman, Kazmi, & Goyal, 2012). Therefore, the sustainability agenda is a pertinent issue that has been increasingly pursued by companies, and it encompasses issues such as environment friendliness or 'green' manufacturing, social responsibility, among others (Reilly & Hynan, 2014). Furthermore, the flow of information affects consumer decision-making and the evaluation of products (Kotler & Armstrong, 2012). Even, social media can significantly change behavior and brand preferences of the consumers (Kohli, Suri, & Kapoor, 2015). For instance, studies show that user generated

content forms the basis of 67% of all consumer goods purchases (Leeflang, Verhoef, Dahlström, & Freundt, 2014). Therefore, it is a logical to conclude that social media is a radical new trend that companies operating in various platforms including online should exploit (Kaplan & Haenlein, 2010). It is important to note that the needs and expectations of the customers have changed. Presently, shopping is more than meeting the normal basic needs such as food, water, and clothing, among others. Furthermore, consumers have increasingly appreciated sustainability, and this is the reason it has had become an important factor of consideration in marketing strategy over the past (Mitchell, Wooliscroft, & Higham, 2010). However, information technology and especially internet has been integrated into daily life thereby increasing efficiency in communication, research, and commerce. As a result, there is need for considerable investments on social media strategies in order to need to not only build a loyal customer base, but also brand ambassadors that can recommend products to others (Leeflang et al., 2014).

Contemporary considerations of marketing strategy have integrated issues of sustainability. It is vital for companies to integrate sustainability in their marketing strategies in order to gain a competitive advantage in the market. Sustainability is envisaged with a future prospect to direct the current efforts and attention to set principles, ethical, and moral values that guide the current conduct (Kumar et al., 2012). It is two-dimensional: temporal and social. While the temporal dimension concerns present and future tradeoffs mainly in issues of the environment, the social dimension addresses trade-offs between consumers and others, commonly contained in the subject of ethics (Grunert, Hieke, & Wills, 2014). The issue of a sustainable tries to make connection between business and environment (Adams, 2006). As figure 1 illustrated below, the assessment sustainability of business practices should be based on environmental, economic, and social dimensions (ConocoPhillips Company, 2006). The reference of economic sustainability pertains to the contribution an organization makes to feasibility of the wider economic system. Environmental sustainability represents the effects of an organization's actions on the physical surrounding and is usually visible to consumers through metrics such as carbon emissions—in other words, being green or environment friendly.

Lastly, social sustainability takes into account the actions of a company and the impact they have on the public or local communities in the surrounding, which include such issues as corporate responsibility, safe working environment, among others (Reilly & Hynan, 2014). Communication forms the basis

sustainability marketing. Particularly, effective internal communication in a company facilitates the implementation of key changes that would make the organization more sustainable. Furthermore, a company that fails to communicate its strategies and initiatives externally (to all stakeholders), risks losing customers as potential customers are increasingly socially and environmentally-conscious (Baldassarre & Campo, 2016). Stakeholders are always eager to know about an organization's sustainable practices. Sustainability reporting is a vital indicator of a firm's commitment to its environmental performance and continuous improvement although it may not reflect sustainable performance. Presently, social media has become an important communication tool for many organizations in regard to sustainability (Reilly & Hynan, 2014). Social media are websites that connect online traffic from the globe with users of similar interests. Such include blogs and applications as YouTube, Twitter, Facebook, and Instagram among others. Current trends show that social media users are increasing. Therefore, companies should also leverage on social media since it has made a considerable impact on e-commerce, consumer behaviors, and business activities (Vafaei & Farkas, 2015). In regard to sustainability, organizations can be viewed as being green or not green. According to Reilly & Hynan (2014), green companies do not only mention their sustainability initiatives more often in their corporate communications, but they are also more active in social media use and more likely to have a consistent corporate presence in social media. Baldassarre & Campo (2016) recommends a self-assessment matrix based on the approach of transparency. This method puts firms in four categories, that is, transparent, translucent, dark, and opaque based on two variables: sustainable commitment and communication. Organizations should consider their sustainable behavior from the perspectives of ethics and general marketing strategy. The implication is that it is not enough to realize sustainability without communicating the efforts and promoting such efforts. Therefore, organizations need to make effort to progress toward a more reliable and effective sustainable status, and perhaps to the transparency quadrant.

Being Sustainable	High commitment	Translucent Companies	Transparent Companies
	Low commitment	Dark Companies	Opaque Companies
		Low-Profile Communication	High-Profile Communication
Appearing Sustainable			

New issues of sustainability

As figure 1 illustrates, Nowadays, more and more sub-categories takes into the account compared to the original categorization – for example, Dannenberg, Frumkin & Jackson (2011) investigated the relationships between the public health, health awareness (one subcategory of social pillar called Safety and health) and sustainability. The researchers defined the mentioned relationships between the people and their environments in the definition of environmental health. Originally, objectives of environmental health are only to control environmental hazards and threats and to promote healthy environments, however, recently environmental health focuses on waste management, built environment, climate change etc. also. Companies need to consider sustainability issues with greater importance. Sustainability efforts yield mutual benefits on the part of the company and its stakeholders especially the customers. One of the important steps for companies in pursuing sustainability is to address respective issues and challenges in the adoption of sustainability in marketing strategy. Although sustainability pertains to ethics, it is becoming increasingly relevant from the perspective of marketing and can be particularly vital in a company’s relationships with stakeholders. On one hand, corporate responsibility is an important criterion to attract customers. However, such behavior is not sufficient and companies should provide comprehensive reports of specific details of the good initiatives carried out when communicating through social media. The reason for this is that the failure of a firm to communicate its strategies and initiative to external stakeholders is likely to lead to loss of sales especially due to the growing number of customers who are socially and environmentally conscious. Accordingly, informing and engaging

employees in the company's sustainability efforts through social media may be an extra benefit to the company in terms of talent retention.

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